

FEATURES OF NON-IONIZING RADIATION DIAGNOSTIC METHODS FOR HYDROCEPHALUS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Modern diagnosis of hydrocephalus in children is one of the most important problems in pediatric neurology and neurosurgery. According to the World Health Organization, the incidence of hydrocephalus in newborns is 1 in 4000. The high proportion of congenital hydrocephalus in the structure of morbidity and mortality among children imposes special requirements on the clinical and instrumental diagnosis of this form of cerebral pathology.*

Currently, neurosonography (NSG) remains a relevant method for diagnosing hydrocephalus in children during the first year of life. The advantages of this method include:

The ability to conduct multiple, daily examinations.

No exposure to X-ray radiation.

The examination can be performed without transporting the child to the machine and does not require the involvement of an anesthesiologist.

Keywords: *neurosonography (NSG), non-ionizing diagnostic methods, perinatal damage, microconvex probes.*

Simplicity and accessibility of performing NSG have significant advantages over other methods used in planned neurosurgery for infants.

Clinical Aspects of Research in Children with Hydrocephalus

In the study of children with hydrocephalus (both active and passive), it is essential to consider the functional features of the vascularization of brain structures. This justifies the need for non-ionizing diagnostic methods, such as NSG, for the in vivo verification of these changes. Early signs of cerebrospinal fluid dynamics disturbance may manifest at various stages of a child's development, leading to neuropsychological and motor disorders, which significantly influence the prognosis of psycho-neurological development.

Problems of Early Diagnosis and Outcomes of Perinatal CNS Damage

Despite the widespread occurrence of perinatal damage to the central nervous system in children, only 15%-20% of such cases are detected in the first days and weeks of life. Adverse outcomes of perinatal CNS injuries are most often associated with insufficient prevention, diagnosis, and inappropriate or untimely treatment, which often leads to passive observation of such children.

The need for early diagnosis and the timely initiation of therapy emphasizes the importance of developing and improving methods that will provide maximum compensation and minimize developmental consequences for the child.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to improve the method of neurosonography in the diagnosis of hydrocephalus in children.

Materials and Methods

An ultrasound study was conducted in the clinic of TashPMI on 49 children aged 1 to 12 months with various cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) dynamic disorders. The studies were performed

using Sonoscape 5000 and Aplio 500 ultrasound diagnostic machines with microconvex probes operating at frequencies of 7.0–12.0 MHz. The results of neurosonography were confirmed using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and multislice computed tomography (MSCT).

For conducting ultrasound of the brain in newborns and young children, no special medication preparation or anesthesia was required. The severity of the child's condition was not a contraindication for performing neurosonography. The probe was placed on the large fontanel of the skull, and scanning was carried out in the coronal plane. By adjusting the probe angle, consecutive sections were obtained through:

A – Frontal lobes

B – Anterior horns of the lateral ventricles

C – Interventricular foramen (Monro's foramen) and the third ventricle

D – Bodies of the lateral ventricles

E – Triangle of the lateral ventricles

F – Occipital lobes

To scan in the sagittal plane, the probe was rotated 90° and by changing its tilt to the right and left, images of the right and left cerebral hemispheres were obtained:

G – Mid-sagittal section through the third and fourth ventricles, corpus callosum, cerebellar vermis, and brainstem

H – Parasagittal section through the caudothalamic notch (probe tilt angle of 10° from the midline section)

I – Parasagittal section through the lateral ventricle (probe tilt angle of 15°-20° from the midline section)

J – Parasagittal section through the "insula" (probe tilt angle of 40°-50° from the midline section)

Analysis of the Echogram. The analysis of the echogram included the assessment of the brain parenchyma, ventricular system, and cisterns, the degree of sulci and pulsation of the cerebral vessels. In cases of additional pathological foci or structures found in the parenchyma, their qualitative characteristics and localization were noted. The echogenicity was classified into echofree (anechoic), increased (hyperechoic), and decreased (hypoechoic) echogenicity, as well as homogeneous and heterogeneous formations.

Research Results

In 49 children examined, ultrasound revealed varying degrees of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) dynamic disorders. Mild hydrocephalus was detected in 11 children, moderate hydrocephalus in 23, and severe hydrocephalus in 15. These cases were characterized by ventricular system dilation in 5 children, brain developmental anomalies in 14, subarachnoid cysts in 2, cerebellar vermis tumors, and cysts in the third and fourth ventricles in 13, polycystic brain disease in 4, cortical and white matter atrophy in 2, and previous inflammatory (6) and hemorrhagic (3) diseases. Periventricular hemorrhage (PVH) grade III was associated with the presence of thrombi in the lateral ventricle lumen, causing its expansion. Grade IV of PVH was characterized by hyperechoic formations with clear contours, located above the body of the lateral ventricle (parenchymal hemorrhage), as well as within its lumen. During dynamic observation, the echostructure of this formation was heterogeneous, eventually forming a porencephalic cyst.

Brain developmental anomalies included: Arnold-Chiari malformation type II in 9 cases, Dandy-Walker anomaly in 3 cases, and Crouzon syndrome in 1 child. All patients underwent

repeated dynamic ultrasound of the brain, with 43 cases showing positive dynamics, while 6 cases showed no improvement after medical therapy or surgical intervention. After cerebrospinal fluid shunting, neurosonography was performed to assess the position of the ventricular catheter end, the presence of hematomas and subdural fluid accumulations (pseudohygrota), ventricular collapse, porencephaly, and other complications.

Conclusions. Neurosonography is an informative method for diagnosing and assessing the severity of brain damage in young children with various forms of cerebrospinal fluid dynamic disorders. Neurosonography allows for the assessment of changes following cerebrospinal fluid shunting surgeries and their complications.

Computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) play a crucial role in objectifying the nature and localization of intracranial hypertension (ICH). However, their use in children is associated with many additional challenges. Therefore, the primary method for visualizing intracranial hypertension remains ultrasound of the brain – neurosonography (NSG).

The most widely accepted technique for the investigation through the large fontanel was proposed by E.G. Grant in 1986. According to the literature, the overdiagnosis of hydrocephalus is related to the fact that, even today, there is no uniform understanding among doctors of different specialties, and even among neurosurgeons, of the pathological process implied when diagnosing hydrocephalus.

Thus, the cause of the development of hydrocephalus is an imbalance between the production and absorption of cerebrospinal fluid, regardless of whether it arises from hyperproduction, impaired absorption, or obstruction of cerebrospinal fluid pathways. The main issue is that more cerebrospinal fluid is produced than absorbed, and the accumulated cerebrospinal fluid, like any additional intracranial volume, leads to increased intracranial pressure and a reduction in the volume of brain tissue. Based on the sequence of events described, the following main symptoms of hydrocephalus can be identified: excessive accumulation of cerebrospinal fluid in the cranial cavity (76%), progressive enlargement of cerebrospinal fluid spaces (83%), high intracranial pressure (91%), and reduced volume of brain tissue (61%).

From this definition, it follows that hydrocephalus always presents with increased intracranial pressure, and thus, in children with post-hemorrhagic hydrocephalus, forms such as normotensive or even hypotensive hydrocephalus do not exist. Cerebrospinal fluid production reduction occurs only when intracranial pressure exceeds 300 mm H₂O, but this happens in terminal situations and does not significantly affect intracranial pressure, as mechanisms that have already become self-sustaining are in place, maintaining intracranial hypertension through the formation of vicious cycles. In other words, if the measures taken to normalize intracranial pressure are insufficient, decompensation occurs, and the process becomes uncontrollable—leading to the development of hydrocephalus.

Considering the above, when there is an imbalance between production and absorption (we are speaking only about communicating hydrocephalus), the fluid entering the ventricles increases the pressure within them, which, with some delay, is transmitted to all cerebrospinal fluid spaces. This leads to an increase in pressure in these spaces and, as a result, the expansion of all cerebrospinal fluid-containing spaces due to compression of the brain parenchyma, but only for a very short period of time, since the brain is a poorly compressible substance, being composed of nearly 80% water.

Neurosonography is a sensitive method for detecting periventricular hemorrhage, intraventricular hemorrhage, periventricular leukomalacia, and meningoencephalitis. The detection of subarachnoid hemorrhage depends on the size and localization of the lesion. Increasing ventriculomegaly and post-hemorrhagic hydrocephalus were observed more frequently in periventricular hemorrhage of the III and IV ventricles. Obstruction was more commonly noted at the level of the aqueduct and Monroe's foramen. In the case of pronounced ventricular dilation, the ventricular index increases.

The identification of intracranial hypertension based on clinical, Dopplerographic data, and direct intracranial pressure measurements, the increase in the volume of the ventricular system, and compression of the subarachnoid spaces allowed differentiation of hydrocephalus from other conditions with similar clinical and endoscopic presentations, avoiding overdiagnosis and the prescription of unjustified treatments.

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